

FLOWABILITY OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) is an important engineering material which has much lower weight than metallic materials with the same strength and toughness, thus the energy consumption can be reduced significantly by using CFRTP as a structural material for transportation. Compared with continuous CFRTP, discontinuous CFRTP requires much lower molding pressure and has higher capacity to form parts with smaller-size or more complex shape, which benefits the reduction of cost and improvement of production efficiency, so it has much more potential to be used for mass production in industrial application. During the fabrication of CFRTP, the flowability of fillers in CFRTP composite is a quite important factor since it decides the mechanical properties of CFRTP materials and molding pressure during manufacture, hence product's reliability and initial investment. In this paper, the flowability of ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT), a kind of discontinuous CFRTP, was investigated. The influence of molding pressure and holding time on the flowability of UT-CTT was investigated first by using mold with ribs. Then the cross section of ribs was observed by microscope in order to characterize the flow behavior of fibers during molding process. The results show that the flowability of UT-CTT changes drastically with different pressure and holding time. Under the conducted pressure, fiber tapes successfully flew into the ribs as U-shape without break and formed a laminate structure as flat part.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) is an excellent material for lightweight vehicles, because of its much less weight with relative high strength compared with traditional metallic materials [1]. It can be used in a wide range of areas, such as engineering, electronics, military, aircraft, racing car and sport equipment. The manufacturing technique of CFRTP for ultra-lightweight vehicles plays an important role in worldwide energy consumption saving and decreasing the CO₂ emission amount [2], so it will be an alternative to the present steel based vehicles manufacturing technique for its environment-friendly application potential in the future. Meanwhile, the freight automobiles with less weight can load more cargo, resulting in larger efficiency and economic benefits with the same energy consumption.

By now, carbon fiber reinforced thermoset (CFRTS), especially CF/epoxy composite, has been developed since a long time ago because of its high strength. However, compared with CFRTP, CFRTS requires much higher costs because of the difficulty in prepreg storage, in-plant recycling and manufacturing by rapid molding technology [3]. Besides, developing CFRTP possesses some important advantages that CFRTS doesn't have. Firstly, CFRTP shows better comprehensive mechanical performance under stress if the interface is adhesive tightly. The energy absorption capacity during fracture of CFRTP is much higher than CFRTS, and the carbon fiber in CFRTP will not delaminated under tensile stress, which occurs in CFRTS and makes it sensitive to stress

concentration [4], so CFRTP is more suitable for high cycle molding, especially for the complex-shape parts. Secondly, the welding joint strength of CFRTP is not weaker than that of bulk material because the concentration of CF at the interface is higher and CF are entangled [5], while CFRTPS can be just bolted or adhesive jointed. Thirdly, owing to the thermoplastic property, it is relatively easier for CFRTP to repair and recycle [6], and the performance of reused parts without delamination of CF is as good as that of new parts [7]. Thus, the production costs and energy needed can be saved significantly, and the wastes during production can be recycled well. Therefore, CFRTP is the better choice than CFRTPS for mass production of lightweight vehicles.

Among kinds of CFRTP materials, discontinuous CFRTP, e.g., chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT), requires much lower molding pressure than continuous CFRTP and has higher capacity to form parts with smaller-size or more complex shape [8]. It benefits the reduction of cost and improvement of production efficiency, so it has much more potential to be used for mass production in industrial application. Additionally unlike conventional CTT, the tapes in ultra-thin CTT (UT-CTT) maintain their rectangle shape after molding. Sato [9] and Zhang [10] investigated the stochastic properties of UT-CTT by Monte Carlo simulation, and showed that the variation of elastic properties is predictable and small enough to apply to primary structure. It is also practical merit of UT-CTT that conventional small specimen can be used to obtain elastic parameters for CAE. Therefore, UT-CTT has much more potential to be used as super lightweight material for complex shape part in industrial application because of its good performance and suitable mechanical properties for CAE.

During fabrication, the flowability of CFRTP is a quite important factor since it decides the mechanical properties of CFRTP and molding pressure [11], hence product's reliability and initial investment. In order to reduce the total cost of CFRTP manufacture, not only faster molding cycle but also lower molding pressure is necessary. It has been known that molding pressure of conventional CTT is lower than both continuous CFRTP and mat reinforced thermoplastics. The first purpose of this paper is to investigate the influence of tape length on required minimum molding pressure. Then flow behavior of the tapes is characterized to establish flow molding simulation of UT-CTT.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

The UT-CTT we studied was prepared using randomly oriented ultra-thin unidirectional prepreg tapes which consisted of carbon fibers and polyamide-6 (PA6) resin, and the thickness of tapes was about 44 μ m. First, the intermediate sheets of chopped tapes were prepared as following processes: (1) Cut the ultra-thin prepreg sheets provided by the Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture into chopped tapes with 5mm width and 12mm, 18mm and 24mm length which were considered in this paper; (2) Dispersed the chopped tapes in water to make them in totally random directions and set them in a plane; (3) Vaporized the undesired water under 110 $^{\circ}$ C for 3min; (4) Pre-pressed the tapes into sheets for handling under around 0.3MPa and 260 $^{\circ}$ C for 1min; (5) Cut the sheets into required size and entirely dried in vacuum. Next, stacked the sheets in mold offered by Sanko Gosei Ltd. as shown in Figure 1 and pressed with 5MPa for 3min and 10MPa for 3min or 10min respectively under the same temperature 260 $^{\circ}$ C to investigate the effect of both pressure and time. In samples (Figure 2), there are two ribs on the plate with length of 30mm and height of 8mm and 3mm respectively. Both of two ribs have a width of 2mm at the top, but the different width at the bottom, i.e., 2.8mm for the taller one and 2.3mm for the shorter one, as shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 1: The mold used for fabrication of UT-CTT samples.

Figure 2: The schematic diagram of plate sample (a) and the size of ribs (b).

Then, the appearance of ribs were observed and scanned by VR-3200 One-Shot 3D Measuring Macroscope. At last, the cross sections of ribs after being polished were observed by microscope, thus the fiber orientation and the flow behavior of UT-CTT could be characterized.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The appearance of tapes after molding

The appearance of UT-CTT fabricated by the molding conditions described above is shown in Figure 3a. It can be seen that the ultra-thin tape whose thickness is just 44 μ m maintains the original rectangular shape without dilacerations and wrinkles after molding. Thus, as stated before, the tape can be simplified in modeling for CAE. On the contrary, as shown in Figure 3b, the conventional CTT made by chopped tapes with thickness of 130 μ m and size of 35 \times 15mm presents a wholly different appearance. The tapes have been squeezed into curved shape. Some tapes are scattered and the original outline of tapes seems hard to distinguish. It makes much more difficult to conduct flow simulation for conventional CTT with this kind of irregular deformation during molding process.

In order to investigate the deformation of tapes when form complex shape, the parts under high magnification of samples were observed in details, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: The tapes after molding of UT-CTT (a) and conventional CTT (b).

Figure 4: The appearance under higher magnification of flat part (a), both inside (b) and outside (c) of one corner of plate and the shaped ribs (d) in molded samples.

In Figure 4a, we can see the tapes in flat part remained the rectangular shape very well and orientated randomly. As for the complex shape, such as the corners of plate (Figure 4b and 4c) and the ribs (Figure 4d), the tapes still remained the rectangle while they were curving as the mold shape, so the carbon fibers in one tape kept parallel during press molding even though forming complex shapes.

Table 1: Molding results of UT-CTT samples with various tape length under different conditions.

Sample	Tape Length/mm	Molding Pressure/MPa	Holding Time/min	Temperature /°C	Results	
					Short Rib	Tall Rib
L12-1	12	5	3	260	×	×
L12-2	12	10	3		○	○
L12-3	12	10	10		○	○
L18-1	18	5	3		×	×
L18-2	18	10	3		○	×
L18-3	18	10	10		○	×
L24-1	24	5	3		×	×
L24-2	24	10	3		×	×
L24-3	24	10	10		○	×

Figure 5: The samples of tapes with 12mm length prepared by molding process under 5MPa for 3min (a), 10MPa for 3min (b) and 10MPa for 10min (c).

Figure 6: The samples of tapes with 18mm length prepared by molding process under 5MPa for 3min (a), 10MPa for 3min (b) and 10MPa for 10min (c).

Figure 7: The samples of tapes with 24mm length prepared by molding process under 5MPa for 3min (a), 10MPa for 3min (b) and 10MPa for 10min (c).

3.2 The influence of tape length and molding condition

The effectiveness of molding was judged by the completeness of rib structure on samples. Table 1 shows the molding results of whether the fabricated ribs has perfect appearance or not, which are represented by circle and cross, respectively. Samples made by ultra-thin tapes with length of 12, 18, 24mm were studied, as shown in Figures 5 to 7, respectively. Three different molding conditions were conducted for samples of same tapes, i.e., 5MPa for 3min, 10MPa for 3min and 10MPa for 10min. Thus, the effect of both molding pressure and holding time could be investigated.

The results show that 5MPa is too low for ribs to shape up in all the samples, as can be seen in Figures 5a, 6a and 7a. 10MPa is also not enough to obtain the perfect taller rib except the samples with 12mm tapes. As shown in Figures 5b and 5c, both the samples of 12mm tapes pressed under 10MPa for 3 and 10min have perfect appearance. However, there is unfilled corner in the samples of 18mm tapes (Figure 6b), even though the main part of the rib can well form. And the unfilled corner still exists when the holding time increases from 3min to 10min (Figure 6c). As for the shorter rib, 10MPa is enough for samples with 12mm and 18mm tapes to shape up, but only the holding time is extended to 10min under 10MPa can the perfect shorter rib in sample with 24mm tapes be obtained (Figure 7c).

In summary, the samples with shorter tapes need lower molding pressure. It indicates that the shorter tapes are easier to flow and form some complex shape during molding process, because of the lower shear stress between shorter tapes. Meanwhile, the flowability of UT-CTT is mainly determined by molding pressure under the same temperature, but the holding time has no so much effect on the flow behavior of UT-CTT. Therefore, the appearance of samples molded under different pressure was scanned by laser in order to observe more details, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: 3D laser scanning results of ribs in samples of 12mm tapes under 5MPa (a) and 10MPa (b), 18mm tapes under 5MPa (c) and 10MPa (d), 24mm tapes under 5MPa (e) and 10MPa (f), all for 3min.

The different colors represent the variation of height. It can be seen clearly that the rib in sample of 12mm tapes molded under 10MPa for 3min has a perfect appearance (Figure 8b), and the imperfect part of the inner corner of the taller rib in sample of 18mm tapes molded under 10MPa for 3min can also be observed (Figure 8d).

In the meantime, the average section area of the taller ribs was calculated from the values measured at 30 positions which are 200 μ m apart in the middle part of ribs, as shown in Figure 9. The results show that the samples of shorter tapes have the larger cross section area of tall rib, no matter the rib has shaped up or not. It further proves that the shorter tapes have better flowability. Besides, the molding pressure also has a huge influence on cross section area of rib. When the pressure changes from 5MPa to 10MPa, the cross section area increases by nearly twice.

Figure 9: The average section area of the 8mm height rib.

3.3 Fiber orientation

Since the sample with 12mm tapes has perfect appearance molded under 10MPa, the cross sections of the samples were prepared and observed, as in Figure 10.

Figure 10: The cross section of ribs in UT-CTT samples of 12mm length tapes molded under 5MPa (a) and 10MPa (b) for 3min.

The results show that the carbon fibers flew as U-shape and formed the rib structure. There are voids and cracks in the ribs pressed under 5MPa (Figure 10a), because the pressure was not high enough to push the tapes to flow more deeply into the mold and the top of rib could not touch the mold.

As a result, the actual temperature at the top of rib was lower than the plate part and the flow behavior was further impeded accordingly. On the contrary, it can be seen in Figure 10b that the carbon fibers in both short and tall ribs pressed under 10MPa were quite compact and well-shaped, so the strength of molded ribs should be much higher than the traditional welded rib structure. Moreover, the fibers in short rib did not flow perpendicularly like in tall rib. It indicates the flow process of fibers. The short rib shaped up first because of its smaller size, and then the more drastic deformation of tall rib required more fibers and resin, so the fibers in short rib was dragged by the fibers in tall rib and finally caused the tortuosity and migration of fibers in short rib.

In addition, the cross sections of one corner of plate in UT-CTT sample of 12mm length tapes molded under 10MPa was also observed, as shown in Figure 11. The result show that the carbon fibers orientate as the mold shape well without any wrinkle or twining, so the mechanical properties obtained by standard specimens can be applicable in CAE to both flat and corner parts made by UT-CTT.

Figure 11: The cross sections of one corner of plate in UT-CTT of 12mm tapes molded under 10MPa.

Although the global stiffness of automotive body is mainly dominated by the flat part, stiffness and strength of the corner parts influence global stiffness and strength as a part of beam structure such as B-pillar. Additionally, though the stiffness of the ribs parts do not affect the structural stiffness, it is important for structural integrity. Therefore, based on the microstructural study in this paper for flat part, corners and ribs, we can insist that UT-CTT has superiority in material selection from viewpoints of both accurate stiffness and strength design.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results can be concluded as follows:

- (1) The ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tapes can keep the original rectangular shape without dilacerations and wrinkles both in flat and complex-shape parts after molding. It benefits the simplification of model for CAE.
- (2) During molding process under the same temperature, the flowability of UT-CTT is mainly determined by tape length and pressure. The UT-CTT of shorter tapes is easier to flow.
- (3) The average section area of the taller rib increases under higher molding pressure, which indicates the better flowability of UT-CTT.
- (4) After molding, carbon fibers flow into the rib as U-shape, so the strength of molded rib structure will be higher than conventional welded one.
- (5) The carbon fibers in corner part orientate as the mold shape well without wrinkle or twining, so the mechanical properties obtained by standard specimens can be applicable to both flat and corner parts made by UT-CTT.

It should be noted that in order to clarify the difference by tape length, we used much smaller ribs than the tapes and normal automobile members. Therefore, the molding pressure and time to fill the rib showed much larger than those to make flat parts. It can be say that UT-CTT can be molded by very low pressure and high speed if parts size and shape are ordinary automotive ones.

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